

Table 2. Average yields of varieties released to the Brazilian Cerrados Region by the Upland Rice Breeding Network compared across states and with checks.

Variety	State	Yield (t/ha)	Yield of check ^b (t/ha)	Yield increase (%)
Araguala	Goiás	2.9 (45) ^a	2.4 [1]	19
BR-4	Piauí	3.2 (6)	2.2 [1]	43
	Amapá	1.6 (3)	1.5 [1]	3
	Roraima	1.9 (4)	1.7 [1]	17
Cabaçu	Goiás	2.7 (36)	2.2 [1]	21
C. América	M. Grosso	2.3 (12)	2.2 [3]	6
Culabana	M. Grosso	1.7 (6)	1.4 [1]	18
Douradão	M. Gerais	3.0 (17)	2.4 [2]	25
EMCAPA 01	E. Santo	3.3 (6)	2.9 [1]	14
Guaporé	Rondonia	3.3 (8)	1.5 [1]	16
Guarani	M. Grosso	2.6 (12)	2.2 [3]	17
	M. Grosso Sul	2.2 (7)	2.1 [3]	6
	Goiás	3.2 (38)	2.7 [1]	16
	M. Gerais	2.5 (11)	1.9 [1]	31
Rlo Paranalba	M. Gross Sul	2.6 (7)	2.4 [1]	5
	Goiás	3.2 (38)	2.7 [1]	16
	M. Gerais	2.5 (11)	1.9 [1]	31
Tangará	M. Grosso	2.3 (21)	2.1 [3]	12
Xingu	Pará	2.5 (9)	2.1 [1]	18
Mean				17.3

^aNumbers in parentheses are number of yield trials. ^bNumbers in brackets represent check: 1 = IAC47, 2 = IAC25, 3 = IAC165.

only 7 yr. This reasonable amount of time was possible because the breeding program uses an off-season site.

Time required for yield trials averaged 3.4 yr, which was 38.6% of total time from crossing to release (Table 1).

Average years required provides a minimum for the safe interpretation of results before release. Yield trials in the Cerrados can be conducted only during the normal growing season and must be replicated over time to better assess the genotype × environment interaction.

We estimated regional yield increases from the network-released varieties by comparing grain yields of new varieties with those of checks in each trial. Percent yield increase was then added and divided by number of varieties, resulting in a 17.3% yield increase (Table 2). Overall mean (average yield of varieties and checks) showed a 20.9% increase. The average was 19.1% when number of trials was considered.

The network provided farmers with several new varieties from 1982 to 1989. Grain yield increased significantly as a result. Total upland rice production would increase by about 1 million t if all farmers used the new varieties on the 3.6 million ha planted to upland rice in Brazil, where current average yield is 1.3 t/ha. ■

Elite upland rice lines in Japan

H. Nemoto, M. Hirayama, K. Okamoto, and M. Miyamoto, Plant Biotechnology Institute, Ibaraki Agricultural Center (IAC), Kamikunij, Mito, Ibaraki 305, Japan

The importance of upland rice is decreasing in Japan. The largest upland rice area grown was 184,000 ha in 1960. Upland rice is now cultivated in rotation with vegetables on about 13,700 ha (0.7% of total cultivated rice area in Japan).

Systematic upland rice breeding in Japan was started in 1929. Since then, about 50 varieties have been bred and released to farmers. Most of the breeding materials came from Japanese traditional upland rice sources, a limited genetic pool.

We started screening for drought tolerance in indica and tropical japonica varieties in 1978 to increase genetic

Characteristics of Kanto-mochi 168 and Kanto-mochi 172, IAC, Japan.

Line/variety	Days to heading	Length (cm)		Blast resistance ^a		Yield (t/ha)
		Culm	Panicle	Leaf	Panicle	
Kanto-mochi 168	125	71	20.1	1	0	4.2
Kanto-mochi 172	126	76	20.5	0	0	4.5
Tsukubahatamochi	124	79	20.8	0	0	4.0

^aBlast resistance scored using scale where 0 = resistant and 9 = susceptible.

variation. We found some drought-tolerant traditional indica, African, and Chinese varieties and crossed them with Japanese upland varieties. Kanto-mochi 168 was bred in 1991 and Kanto-mochi 172 in 1992. (See table for important characteristics of these lines.) Kanto is the area code of our breeding team and mochi means glutinous in Japanese.

Kanto-mochi 168 was selected from the cross of JC81 (a traditional indica variety introduced from IRR) and Norin-mochi 4 (a Japanese upland variety) that was backcrossed twice.

Kanto-mochi 168 is more tolerant of water stress than Japanese varieties and has outstanding cooking quality.

Kanto-mochi 172 was bred from the cross of African upland rice variety IRAT109 and Japanese upland variety Tsukubahatamochi. The cooking quality of this line is not as good as that of other varieties, but its yield ability is excellent.

We are evaluating these lines in local adaptability tests. They will be useful genetic donors in future upland rice breeding. ■